

Appendix F: Additional tables

Table F.3. Observing times discarded from the CARMENES time series. Further details in Sect. 2.1.

BJD - 2 400 000	Reason
59483.611306	Drift
59490.496133	Drift
59568.353089	Moon
59775.658997	Drift
59809.637907	S/N < 20
59864.638976	Moon
59896.425823	Moon
59948.335626	Moon
59951.349542	Drift
60217.526971	Moon
60270.343849	S/N < 20
60272.336330	Moon
60274.457653	Moon
60276.326409	Moon
60302.379642	Moon
60307.375308	NZP
60555.574195	NZP

Table F.4. Summary of the ASAS-SN observations of KOBE-1. See Sect. 2.3.

Start date	End date	Camera	Band	Station	Location	#Obs
05 May 2013	29 Nov 2018	bb	V	Brutus	Haleakala Observatory	421
03 Dec 2018	30 Jan 2022	bB	g	Brutus	Haleakala Observatory	161
29 Oct 2017	11 Sep 2018	bf	V	Cassius	Cerro Tololo International Observatory	6
02 Nov 2018	14 Aug 2024	bF	g	Cassius	Cerro Tololo International Observatory	68
29 Nov 2017	16 Nov 2023	bj	g	Henrietta Leavitt	McDonald Observatory	126
28 Nov 2017	03 Aug 2024	bn	g	Cecilia Payne	South African Astrophysical Observatory	116
22 Sep 2017	18 Aug 2024	br	g	Bohdan Paczyński	Cerro Tololo International Observatory	212

Table F.6. Prior distributions for the kima RV analysis. Subscript i identifies the planet. See Sect. 4.1.1.

Parameter	Prior
m [$\text{m s}^{-1} \text{d}^{-1}$]	$\mathcal{G}(0, 0.01)$
q [$\text{m s}^{-1} \text{d}^{-2}$]	$\mathcal{G}(0, 10^{-5})$
γ [m s^{-1}]	$\mathcal{U}(-23\,341, -23\,241)$
σ_{jit} [m s^{-1}]	$\mathcal{LU}(0.01, 40)$
ν^a	$\mathcal{LU}(2, 1000)$
N_p	$\mathcal{U}(0, 3)$
P_i [d]	$\mathcal{LU}(1.0, 1157.9)$
K_i [m s^{-1}]	$\mathcal{U}(0, 27)$
e_i	$\mathcal{K}^c(0.881, 2.878)$
ϕ_i^b	$\mathcal{U}(0, 2\pi)$
ω_i	$\mathcal{U}(0, 2\pi)$

Notes. ^(a) Prior for the Student-t likelihood degrees of freedom. ^(b) True anomaly at the first observation. ^(c) $\mathcal{K}$ represents the Kumaraswamy prior (Kumaraswamy 1980).

Table F.8. Prior and posterior distributions for the 2p1c2c + GP model for the S-BART RVs. See Sect. 4.1.2.

Parameter ^a	Prior	Posterior
m [$\text{m s}^{-1} \text{d}^{-1}$]	$\mathcal{U}(-0.05, 0.05)$	$-(7.6 \pm 4.3) 10^{-3}$
q [$\text{m s}^{-1} \text{d}^{-2}$]	$\mathcal{U}(-0.01, 0.01)$	$-(7.9 \pm 3.6) 10^{-6}$
γ [m s^{-1}]	$\mathcal{U}(-23\,330.6, -23\,255.7)$	$-23\,295.3^{+1.1}_{-1.2}$
σ_{jit} [m s^{-1}]	$\mathcal{MLU}(1.9, 24.9)$	$2.11^{+0.37}_{-0.35}$
m_{PX}	$\mathcal{U}(-0.05, 0.05)$	$(8.9 \pm 4.0) 10^{-5}$
q_{PX}	$\mathcal{U}(-0.01, 0.01)$	$-8.0 \pm 3.2) 10^{-8}$
γ_{PX}	$\mathcal{U}(0.30, 0.53)$	$0.3978^{+0.0100}_{-0.0098}$
$\sigma_{\text{jit,PX}}$	$\mathcal{MLU}(10^{-3}, 7.4 \cdot 10^{-2})$	$(3.86^{+0.70}_{-0.68}) 10^{-3}$
P_b [d]	$\mathcal{LU}(1.1, 100.0)$	$8.5400^{+0.0037}_{-0.0036}$
K_b [m s^{-1}]	$\mathcal{U}(0.0, 14.0)$	3.78 ± 0.50
$T_{0,b}$ [d]	$\mathcal{U}(2\,459\,397.6, 2\,459\,497.6)$	$2\,459\,415.94^{+0.31}_{-0.33}$
e_b	Fixed to 0	
P_c [d]	$\mathcal{LU}(1.1, 100.0)$	$29.675^{+0.052}_{-0.054}$
K_c [m s^{-1}]	$\mathcal{U}(0.0, 14.0)$	3.49 ± 0.48
$T_{0,c}$ [d]	$\mathcal{U}(2\,459\,397.6, 2\,459\,497.6)$	$2\,459\,448.2 \pm 1.2$
e_c	Fixed to 0	
$\eta_{1,\text{RV}}$ [m s^{-1}]	$\mathcal{U}(0.0, 14.0)$	$0.70^{+0.80}_{-0.50}$
$\eta_{1,\text{PX}}$	$\mathcal{U}(0.0, 0.06)$	$(1.26^{+0.24}_{-0.43}) 10^{-2}$
η_2 [d]	$\mathcal{U}(56.1, 3540.2)$	83^{+17}_{-23}
η_3 [d]	$\mathcal{G}_t(37.4, 6.0)$	$37.90^{+0.99}_{-0.86}$
η_4	$\mathcal{LU}(10^{-2}, 10.0)$	$0.75^{+0.21}_{-0.37}$

Notes. ^(a) PX denotes the proxy used, in this case being CaIRT₂. ^(b) Mode of the marginalized posterior distribution at 0.

Table F.9. Integration times for the LIFESim simulations. See Sect. 5.4.2.

Planet type	Configuration	$t_{\text{int, KOBE-1 b}}$	$t_{\text{int, KOBE-1 c}}$
Super-Earth	Optimistic	15 min	45 min
	Baseline	1 h	4 h
	Pessimistic	13 h	44 h
Mini-Neptune	Optimistic	5 min	10 min
	Baseline	20 min	50 min
	Pessimistic	4 h	9 h

Table F.10. Priors and posteriors of the analysis of the TESS light curve assuming Gaussian priors on the period from the RV analysis. See Sect. 4.2.

Parameter	Prior	Posterior
<i>Inferred parameters</i>		
Orbital period, P_b [d]	$\mathcal{G}(29.64, 0.040)$	$29.640^{+0.039}_{-0.040}$
Time of mid-transit, $T_{0,b} - 2\,400\,000$ [d]	$\mathcal{U}(58\,764.0, 58\,773.0)$	$58\,768.6582^{+3.0205}_{-0.0047}$
Orbital inclination, i_b [deg.]	$\mathcal{U}(70.0, 90.0)$	$89.210^{+0.139}_{-0.075}$
Planet radius, R_b [$R_{\oplus}$]	$\mathcal{U}(0.0, 10.0)$	1.69 ± 0.12
Stellar radius, $R_{\star}$ [$R_{\odot}$]	$\mathcal{G}(0.619, 0.011)$	$0.619^{+0.011}_{-0.011}$
Stellar mass, $M_{\star}$ [$M_{\odot}$]	$\mathcal{G}(0.629, 0.017)$	$0.631^{+0.018}_{-0.016}$
<i>Derived parameters</i>		
Transit depth, Δ_b [ppt]	(derived)	$0.60^{+0.13}_{-0.21}$
Orbit semi-major axis, a_b [au]	(derived)	$0.1608^{+0.0014}_{-0.0016}$
Relative orbital separation, $a_b/R_{\star}$	(derived)	$55.9^{+1.1}_{-1.1}$
Impact parameter, $b_b/R_{\star}$	(derived)	$0.769^{+0.136}_{-0.065}$
Incident Flux, $F_{\text{inc,b}}$ [$F_{\text{inc},\oplus}$]	(derived)	$3.89^{+0.43}_{-0.39}$
Equilibrium temperature, $T_{\text{eq,b}}$ [K]	(derived)	$356.7^{+9.4}_{-9.3}$

References

Kumaraswamy, P. 1980, *Journal of Hydrology*, 46

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